

STRENGTH PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE LAMINATE UNDER BIAXIAL LOADINGS

Ipeei Susuki

Airframe Division, National Aerospace Laboratory
7-44-1 Jindaiji Higashi-machi, Chofu-shi, Tokyo 182, Japan

ABSTRACT

The strength properties under biaxial loadings were studied analytically and experimentally for fiber reinforced plastic composite laminates. The testing machine, composed of two pairs of hydraulic actuators which are attached horizontally in a stiffened frame, enabled independent in-plane orthogonal static and fatigue loadings by mean of optimized load/positioning feed-back control system. A two-dimensional finite element method was prepared for designing the specimen configuration. Our limited static test results indicate a similar strength envelope to the analytically estimated strength envelopes based on the quadratic failure criterion. The significant strength reduction was observed under out-of-phase biaxial fatigue tests.

1. INTRODUCTION

The application fields of composite structures has been increasingly expanded in the past few decades especially for the structures where weight is at a premium. Laminated plates of fiber reinforced plastics are widely adopted to the composite structures as load bearing components. They have the advantage that their mechanical properties can be tailored through fiber orientations, ply thickness ratios, and stacking sequences. This capability gives a designer an additional degree of flexibility to obtain the desired strength or stiffness.

In general, the load-bearing components in many practical structures are subjected to more complex loading than uniaxial one. However, most available strength information is based on uniaxial stress state[1][2]. It is well known that the strength of composite laminates can be changed steeply with a given set of combined stresses[3][4]. Efficient and reliable designs require a thorough understanding of strength characteristics of multidirectional composite laminates under complex loading.

Several failure criteria have been proposed[5][6], which are applicable to un-isotropic composite materials. Among these failure criteria, the maximum stress and the maximum strain criteria are the most widely used in practice and, the other hand the quadratic criterion[5][7] has received the widest attention among researchers[8]. There does not seem to be a well-established data base on the strength of composite laminates, and the need still exists for experimental data on the fracture behavior of composite materials under combined stress state.

The development of specimen which can generate any desired stress state in the gauge area is the first step for strength evaluation of composite laminate under combined stress state. Various kinds of specimens have been proposed and used to obtain combined biaxial load test data for metallic alloys[1]. The most common method of biaxial testing employs the thin-walled tube subjected to combined axial and torsional loads, with internal and external pressures[9][10]. However, in some cases such as strength optimized composite plate, in-plane loadings may be better way of biaxial loading[11][12]. Using cruciform specimen is alternative method for biaxial test. It is well known that the cruciform specimens with a reduced-thickness center section and with slotted arms show good uniform stress/strain field in gauge area, but such designing may not be always applicable to material test of composite laminates[12].

Our previous studies[13][14] indicate that the stress state in the center area of composite cruciform specimen is not always predictable from the biaxial loads given at each tab, and can be affected by geometric parameters and also mechanical properties of the laminates which makes the gauge area and surrounding area. A computer aided designing for cruciform composite specimen had to be developed to study the relation between biaxial loads at tab ends and stresses in the gauge area for several kinds of specimens, and find an optimum configuration for strength evaluation of composite laminate for structural components.

Figure 1. Strength surface of a quasi-isotropic T300/5208 laminate

Figure 2. Strength surface of a quasi-isotropic APC2 laminate

2. STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS OF LAMINATES UNDER IN-PLANE STRESSES

The usual assumption of the symmetrically laminated plate theory is used with first ply failure envelope based on the quadratic failure criterion[5]. The strength of laminate for a given set of in-plane combined stresses is evaluated by examining the minimum strength ratio R among plies in a laminate. This value R can be interpreted that the weakest ply in a laminate has a strength margin by R times for the given stresses. Figure 1 shows the R -value surface of the quasi-isotropic laminates of graphite/epoxy (T300/5208) which has a unit thickness for normalized tension dominated region. The similar analytical result for graphite/PEEK (APC2) is shown in Figure 2. The strength surface of quasi-isotropic laminates makes gently-sloping surfaces for both materials.

Given a set of in-plane combined stresses, we can design an optimized laminate by selecting fiber orientations and ply thickness ratios. The laminates, studied in this work, are limited to be symmetric, and consist of plies with 0, 90, 45 and -45 degree fiber orientations. An attempt is made to find the optimal combination of maximum of four ply groups to obtain the maximum strength for a given set of stresses.

Figure 3 and 4 are the same R -values for the optimized laminates. These figures show the maximum strength values by optimization. We need to select the proper combination of plies to make the most of composite laminates. The ply groups to be selected to obtain the maximum strength for a given set of stresses are shown in Figure 5 and 6, respectively. In both cases for graphite/epoxy and graphite/PEEK laminates, numerical calculation results show that the laminate consists of 0, 45 and -45 ply orientations gives higher strength values for wide variety of in-plane biaxial stresses (S_1, S_2) without shear stress.

Figure 3. Strength surface of the optimized T300/5208 laminate

Figure 4. Strength surface of the optimized APC2 laminate

Figure 5. Territorial map of optimized ply groups for T300/5208 laminate

Figure 6 Territorial map of optimized ply groups for APC2 laminate

Figure 7. Schematic view of biaxial testing machine with control system diagram

3. IN-PLANE BIAXIAL TESTING

The biaxial testing machine consists of four hydraulic actuators of 200kN (tension/compression) capacity each for static and fatigue loads. These four actuator assemblies make two pairs, and are rigidly mounted in an octagonal box-shaped frame diagonally (Figure 7). Each loading axis

is called x- and y-axis in this report. The frame is of heavy duty welded construction, and placed horizontally. Available testing space between pairs of actuators is about 1000 mm. A load cell and a linear variable differential transformer(LVDT) are installed in each actuator assembly. The components purchased from SCHENK Corporation, Germany, include the four hydraulic actuator assemblies, manifolds, the control console and a hydraulic pump unit.

To minimize a rigid movement, or shift of the center of the specimen, during biaxial static and fatigue tests, the machine was not only controlled by load signals but also by positioning signals. The control system of X1 and X2 actuators which generate the x-axis load in pairs, is shown schematically in Figure 7. For example, a load command signal FX will be mixed with feedback signals(FX1 and FX2). These feedback signals are computed from F1,F2,S1 and S2 signals by computation circuit CX1 and CX2, where F1 and S1 are the load cell and LVDT out put of X1 actuator, and F2 and S2 are those of X2 actuator.

The composite laminates are more vulnerable for the drift of the specimen than conventional isotropic materials because the strength along one axis can be much less than the other perpendicular axis. A small rigid movement during the test can give unexpected damages to some weak plies in a laminate. It seems to be difficult to control four actuators not generate imbalance at all by load feed-back signals only.

A double loop feed-back control system was developed to carry out static tests and also long term fatigue tests with high stability and accuracy, and without readjustments of position of specimen. The machine can perform any uni-axial fatigue test, where only one pair of opposing arms of cruciform specimen will be held and loaded and the other pair of arms will be free. The center of a cruciform specimen was almost stationary, less than 0.04 mm drift, during a preliminary fatigue test.

Figure 8. Mesh generation examples for designing cruciform specimen

4. DESIGNING CRUCIFORM SPECIMEN

An attempt was made to develop a computer aided design system for establishing the desirable configuration of cruciform specimen to estimate mechanical behaviors and strength under biaxial stress states. All the computer codes were described by C language and can run on personal computers of MSDOS operating system.

Figure 9. Input parameters for designing laminate cruciform specimen

Figure 10. Comparison of stress curves by ADINA and the prepared solver

Figure 11. Example of numerical analysis of stress distribution in a specimen

These programs are divided into three parts. The first one as a pre-processor makes up a specimen configuration by minimum geometric inputs, which are (1) radius or width and thickness of gauge area, (2) radius or width and thickness of surrounding, (3) radius of shoulders and (4) length and width of tab area. After interactive editing and modifying specimen geometry on the screen, the processor will generate a mesh for finite element method (FEM) analysis. Figure 8 shows some examples of mesh generation by this pre-processor.

Laminate properties such as ply materials, ply numbers, fiber orientations, stacking sequence are given for gauge and surrounding areas respectively. As shown schematically in Figure 9, the laminate of surrounding area does not have to be the same laminate as the gauge area. We judged the accuracy of our FEM program, using eight-node isoparametric elements, by comparison with ADINA program. Figure 10 shows an example of a good agreement between

the stress component S_y along the x-axis by ADINA and that of our program. Stress distribution in a candidate cruciform specimen is shown in Figure 11. Higher stresses are obtained in the central area as being expected by reducing the thickness and changing the stacking sequences.

5. STRENGTH PROPERTIES UNDER BIAxIAL LOADINGS

The static and fatigue strength properties of laminates are investigated. The biaxial load ratio at tabs and generated stress ratio in the central area is generally different, which is dependent on materials, stacking sequences, and specimen configurations. Strain gauge measurements were necessary to obtain the given combination of in-plane stresses during the tests. Our limited static test results are shown in Figure 12, which indicate a similar strength envelope to the analytically estimated strength envelopes based on the quadratic failure criterion (Tsai-Wu failure criterion). It is not easy to estimate the failure strains experimentally. As is seen in Figure 13, no strain gages attached in the central area of specimen could survive until the last stage of deformation. The failure strains are estimated by the assumption that the specimen is linearly elastic up to failure.

Figure 12 Failure strains of APC2 laminates with the quadratic failure criterion

Figure 13 Example of load-strain curve of APC2 laminate under biaxial test

Figure 14 Phase difference between tabs and central area during out-of-phase biaxial fatigue test

Figure 15 Fatigue strength of APC2 laminates under biaxial loading

The fatigue strength of composite laminate under biaxial cyclic stresses is a function of phase difference. It is not always easy to obtain an expected fatigue stress phase in the central region of cruciform specimen which makes gage area. Generally, the phase of cyclic stresses in the center area does not coincide with the load phase at tab where the fatigue loads are input to each loading axis. The longitudinal and transverse Poisson's ratios effect a phase difference between two axes. Figure 14 shows an example of phase shift characteristics of laminates. Only in-phase and reverse-phase, which means 180 degree shift between x- and y-axes, the stress phase in the central area is the same as those of the load in tab-end area. Our limited experimental data shows that the effect of phase on fatigue strength is considerably severe as is shown in Figure 15.

6. CONCLUSIONS

1. A biaxial testing machine with double loop control system was developed.
2. A computer aided designing of composite cruciform specimen is necessary for reliable biaxial strength evaluations
3. Biaxial stresses in the gage area of cruciform specimen are not straight forward from the load at each tab end.
4. The significant strength reduction was observed under out-of-phase biaxial fatigue tests.

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